

UTILIZATION OF ITEM ANALYSIS INDICES TO CORROBORATE CRITICAL THINKING SCALE FOR UNIVERSITY STUDENTS GLOBAL CHANGE

Dr. Wali, Dorathy Wokunuchi and Dr. Ogunka Richard I.

Department of Educational Psychology, Guidance and Counseling in the Faculty of Education, Ignatius Ajuru
University of Education, Rivers State, Nigeria

Email: ldorasun@yahoo.com, lheanyirichie@gmail.com

Phone Number: 08066414626, 08054626727

July 7th, 2025

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16761336>

Abstract: This study was focused on using item analysis indices for corroboration of critical thinking scale developed by Sunday, Dorathy in the year 2021; to determine the authenticity of the multiple choice items generated for university students global change, South-South Geo-Political zone Nigeria was the study area. Three research questions governed this study, and the study adopted an ex-post facto design; based on the secondary instrument on critical thinking scale. Multistage sampling procedure of three (3) stages; purposive, proportionate stratified and purposive were used to draw the sample of 1, 0 41 participants from the population. A reliability coefficient of 0.87 was gotten from the pilot study. The difficulty, discriminative and distractive indices were methods used to analyze the research questions. Based on the results; the item difficulty indices ranged from 0.71 to 0.27. While discriminating indices ranged from 0.61 to 0.15 and the distractive indices ranged from 0.89 to 0.32 respectively; for the fifty (50) items on SCTS. Conclusively, SCTS is authentic; because it has very good ranges of its difficulty, discriminative and distractive indices for university students in the globe. Recommendations were made that; evaluators or psychometricians should always find out the authenticities of developed instrument; especially, on item analysis indices to be sure of its goodness of the items. Other stake holders, such as; Tertiary institutions, WAEC; NECO and different measurement and evaluation bodies or departments in business areas; should regularly invite experts in measurement and evaluation disciplines to corroborate their instruments for positive changes in the globe.

Key Words: Utilization, Item Analysis Indices, corroborate, Critical Thinking, University Students

Sub-theme: Innovative Research; Critical Thinking is one of the vital innovative areas (skills) that can bring about positive changes for university students in Nigeria and the globe.

Introduction

Item analysis is a systematic process of determination of student's answers to an individual item in a test to ensure quality of the item entirely, the essence of this item analysis indices is to facilitate the item that will be used in the future test and eliminate ambiguity or the items that may not lead the test taker rightly in a single administration, so it helps in covering a particular aspect of the content of the domain where the item answered

are compared with the whole scores of the test (www.washington.edu/assessment/scoring-scoring/scoring/reports/item-analysis/.retrieved 5th march, 2019). Item analysis is a method of evaluating the effectiveness of a scale item which can be achieved by various guided principles such as the item difficulty, item discriminating and the item distracter indices. This enables the scale researcher to ascertain the difficulty of each item through the percentage of the sample answering the scale that response to the item right for indication of high or low value in order to find out the simple or difficult items accordingly as well as measuring the extent of good item discriminating in a similar view. Also, it is formal analysis to study students answers or responses to individual item for improvement of the scale quality and the items in the bank to see if the items are very easy and are also discriminating accordingly as well as distracting the students in the right directions (<https://www.uwosh.edu/testing/faculty-information/test-scoring/scoring/score-reportinterpretation> retrieved 5thmarch, 2019).

From the concept of item analysis, the basic steps which are guides in the realization of the analysis of this study includes: the item difficulty indices of the item, item discriminating indices and the item distracter indices of each of the item accordingly. Difficulty indices is a representation of the percentage of respondents that answered the items correctly, it shows that if the value is high, most of the respondents answered the question correctly while the low value means that most of them choose the wrong item but if many are correctly answered it reveals that the items are easy.

(Melyabeen, Hassan, Butt and Rizvic, 2018). In contrast, this will not be considered, rather the difficulty indices in this scale may be determined by the correct options chosen, divided by the total number of the items.

It is necessary to say that difficulty indices are purposeful in diver's ways in that it indicate the concept that require to be reemphasized when discover that students cannot answer most questions right because they are hard and it is an identification of the strength and weakness of the construct or domain given feedback from the students on the aspect as well as revealing the item bias; Anon (2006) in Johan, Sahari, Wahab, Abdullah, Abdullah, Omar and Muhamad (2011). This analysis also functions in discovering the ability of an item that really discriminates between the respondents who knows the right answer from others. Findings has revealed that difficulty indices that ranges from 0.69 to 0.79 and above are high but if it is less the result goes beyond the listed range from a study that investigates a difficulty index, sensitivity and specificity of long case and multiple choice questions to predict student's proficiency (MRCPCH and Yus, 2014). On the other hand, discriminating indices is the establishment of how well the scale item differentiates between the test respondents who have learnt very well and those that have not learnt much, the high proficient students from the low proficient concerning the construct under study and to achieve this, the researcher can apply various methods for computation of items that discriminates; of which point biserial correlation is one of them to find out the respondent performance of a specific whether it is right or wrong to choose he or she made as well as the persons score in total, scale item that is very discriminating shows that the respondent that answered the right item has also performed well in the test while those that answered the item wrongly may have as well done badly in the entire test (www.proftesting.com/test-topics/steps-a.php. 5th march, 2019). Discriminating is good if the extent to which students with high total test score also hard a specific item right and it is also called item effect because it is an item that reveals effectiveness in discrimination of students that mastered the domains from others (Iweka, 2014). More so, the discriminating item indices may be most times ranging positively or negatively such like; -1.0-10, in this study if an item discriminate in the negative direction, it will mean that majority of the respondents who have achieved more or who can adequately think critically may be choosing the wrong answers, while those who

did not really think critically as it may show in their responses chose the item correctly. This may be revealing to the researcher that the items are not measuring what it is supposed to measure or it could be as a result of misappropriation of the key. Just like item difficulty, the result of the item discrimination can be interpreted in recognition of a relationship between an item difficulty indices and its discriminating indices, from this study if an item of the scale has a very high or very low p-value, the future value of the discriminating indices may be less than, if the item has an average p-value, that is to say that very simple or very difficult item may not discriminate, whereas if majority will have high value they may discriminate ranging from 0.0-0.3.

However, discrimination indices can be estimated by minus the number of students in the lower group who choose the right answer from the number of students in the upper group who choose the right answer and later divide by the number of students in individual group. Item discrimination may be said to have power when a good item can discriminate between the students who will answer well in the scale and those who may not do well and to estimate the power of discrimination of a particular item by the discriminating indices of the item represented by D and the coefficient of the discrimination, in determining in the D the number of students who will answer the item correct from the high score group will be compared with the number of students who will answer the same item right from the low group. In order words, if the item is discriminating in the appropriate direction, more of the students that will be in high score group will be getting that item right than the other low group (PPUKM, 2015). In computation of discrimination indices also known as D, the researcher needs to first of all score individual students test after which the researcher ranks them and arranges them in ascending or descending order and find the 27% (percent) of the total students who and answer the scale administered and separate or remove the 27% of the students upper and also do same to the 27% of students lower, the 27% (percent) revealed that the value may be increase differences in the normal distribution while producing adequate cases for analysis with the use of many respondents for stability realization (Wiersma and Jurs 1990 in ericae.net accessed 6th march, 2019).

The third stage of item analysis for this study is the item distracter indices, they are wrong options combined with the key of a particular item, it is used to find out the efficiency of distracters which may lead students not to choice the correct answer and their individual name is distracter (Kpolovie 2014). This type of analysis reveals a measure of the extent each of the correct options contribute to increase the adequacy of a multiple choice item unlike the difficulty indices and the item discriminating indices, the item distracter checks the proficiency of the incorrect response items where the incorrect distracters are clearly not correct or plausible to actually look like the correct answer to the students who is not sure of the correct answer that has not gotten better understanding of what was taught but if the distracter cannot perform the functions of representing the right answer for most students to select it, it implies that answers are easy or simple.

The essence of utilization of distracter involves that are plausible based on students misconceptions as part of item analysis which identifies the number of students that chooses each option, in order to have adequate information of distractor the researcher are expected to indicate the item difficulty and consider the respondents for each item just like where there four options for individual item that may have been chosen from between only two, this may show that other items of distracter were not effective and this can also be simple for those students who do not gain much to consciously reduce the options either from four to three or two which may result to guessing the right answers and if about two or more items are in the options are not chosen it may be imply that the items are not distractive enough, in this context students who have accurate understanding of the demand and this can be achieved ascertaining if the best is attracted to choose the wrong answer. Item distracter may be functional or effective where about three options out of four options of a stem are not correct that may be choosing

to very low percentage of respondents or more of them and the efficiency of distractor may range from about (Sing, 2017).

In terms of similarity, distractor may be regarded as a quality identification of item difficulty and it is not supposed to be chosen by the students who are doing well and overlook by the respondents who know the right answers but it may be misleading students if it is always selected by the group of respondents who should choose the right answer. The number of options that are chosen less than 5% (percent) of the respondents are some of the items that are not functioning effectively as distractors of which some may be revised or discard (Abdulghani et al., 2014).

Notwithstanding, for proper corroboration of critical thinking scale developed by SCTS (2021) using item analysis indices; the absence of reviewing the philosophical perception of critical thinking in this study may render the research work incomplete or reduce the quality as an advance research, because critical thinking skills are best defined by philosophers (Marcelo, 2023). Hence, it is proper to understand the philosopher's opinions about the construct understudy. In their views from the origin, it has been explained as a set of education also known as reflective thinking where students need to be active and being conscious of value or what they believe based on what has been known already; that the vital role of critical thinking has led to its adoption in higher schools; like the universities and the educational objectives designed by Bengamine Bloom (1956) of his six taxonomy recognized critical thinking as it has equally required of high level students to study it as a course which has been commissioned by America Philosophical Association (1987) that critical thinking should be taken for accurate assessment and teaching of students.

In that regard, Stanovich et al. (2010) explained the concept of critical thinking as being rational by understanding the combination of individual believe to real life and that students who think critically have the propensity or potentials over others answers from their independent minds, they continued; that it may also serve as an inquiry (Bailin et al, 2009). Educationally, critical thinkers have an edge in realizing the goals of education with its criteria and standards for the type of thinking that may occur as it includes reorganization, adoption and implementation. However, the process through which critical thinking can take place in different stages by students where stated in suggesting their opinions, as their minds will be eager to proffer solutions with an intellectual reasons to solve problems with questioning or making a tentative guess as a guide to find information as to engage them in mental reasoning in different dimensions and make inferences as cited in (Dewey, 1933), the process made up of unique mental and states for indication of students' abilities, skills, disposition, attitude the habit they display and this can prepare students. Again the educational goals and device mean to determine the degree to which they have learnt to find out if they have gained, so these includes the observation of the things happening in once environment, having feelings about something and proffering solutions that satisfies the questions emotionally. In details, critical thinking can manifest in different form of dispositions such as having open mind, attitude that may be regarded as virtue of behavior in terms of how students would think is the most important which is the criteria's of critical thinkers of which some are antecedence. Sunday and Orluwene (2021); possibility or having the inclinations to think in a specific direction no matter the condition the disposition of a critical thinking has to be instigated both intrinsic and extrinsic that will gradually mature and these set of students value and enjoy the use of their knowledge and ability to think things through in the task as task to them as they are always committed and eager to inquire. Their dispositions works in divers areas may be some will open to religion while some will have self-confidence some in sciences (Bailin 2009, Hamby 2014). Even their ability to have courage will eliminate the phobia of doing something intellectually and being willing to ensure that a judgment that may be

about taking place does not hold in the sense that matters are not supposed to end without adequate treatment Orluwene and Sunday (2020), students can hold on to critical thinking with alternative measures, having trust in once self-reasoning not feeble thinking that will produce.

The dispositions of critical thinking for students includes knowledge; to systematically follow the guidelines of any objective critically and understand students contributions are necessary for what has been observed, inferred, ambiguous words needs to be questioned if understood on how to conclude, induce and deduce issues of all situation, conception of both null and alternate hypotheses to assume and predict what next to take place statistically the experiment and investigate observation variables and to argue or analyze, the need to be precise, assume, conclude, premises (Black, 2012). It can be deduced that crucial thinking skills can be improved from some standard instrument outcomes based on the validity and reliability when the instrument measures what it is supposed to measure. However, the scholastic opinion about critical thinking is beyond the objectives of the school courses expected of the students to learn at school, they are of the view that critical thinking should be generalize by teaching it as an independent course in the school rather than to allow let the students practice it in the course of study alone since individual courses are aimed at various objectives (Standford Encyclopedia of Philosophical, 2018). Above all, whether critical thinking is to be learned or assess in the students courses of study; there is need to verify the quality of the instrument developed on critical thinking; in order to be sure that the expected knowledge and the task required of the students can be attained at all times and anywhere in the world.

For this study; using item analysis indices to corroborate critical thinking scale for university students, the current ill situation is that some examining bodies, universities and other institutions that uses testing instruments do not really border to be sure of the testing instruments they use to examine candidates or students, basically on the goodness or authenticity of the multiple choice items that needs to follow the right systematic process of generating items by considering the properties of item indices such as; difficulty, discriminating and distractive indices respectively; as discovered by the researcher through her experiences and observation. Also, some psychometricians construct or develop very easy difficult items, they do not also ascertain if the items are discriminating effectively, and they overlook the fact that the wrong stems in the options are supposed to distract (distractors or wrong) students who are not very sure of the correct answers, rather; they end up muddling all the items together. Several approaches has been laid down to eliminate these bottlenecks through other researchers that have executed studies on; evaluating the quality of multiple choice questions via difficulty and discrimination index, and discovered that the relationship of MCQs instrument that contains good difficulty and discrimination as well as its distractors effectiveness had high percentage and acceptable; while about 19% were very easy and very difficult, this means that the users of the instrument are sure of it (Mahjabeen, Alam and Hassan, 2018). Also, another study on difficulty and discrimination indices of sample of typical multiple choice questions administered to students at different levels found disparity in both analysis, it was concluded that typical MCQs may produce a typical value based on their background differences, experiences, this affirms that corroboration of developed instruments, very importantly MCQi on metacognitive is highly welcomed in innovative research etc (Tare, Semeh and samihan 2018). However, the concern of the researcher in this study; is to verify or find out if the fifty multiple choice items which was developed by Sunday, Dorathy in the year 2021 met the appropriate criteria's that a developed instrument of such should possess as regards the difficulty levels, if the items discriminated effectively without confusing the respondents, as well as check whether the items distractors actually distracted the respondents who do not really think critically to select the correct answers.

The aim of this study was to corroborate the goodness, effective or authenticity of critical thinking scale developed by Sunday Dorathy; using item analysis indices. Specifically, the objective of this study was to: Determine the difficulty indices of the Sunday's critical thinking scale (SCTS) items. Ascertain the discriminating indices of the Sunday's critical thinking scale (SCTS) items. Find out the distracter indices of the Sunday's critical thinking scale (SCTS) items.

Research Questions

1. What are the difficulty indices of the Sunday's critical thinking scale (SCTS) items?
2. What are the discriminating indices of the Sunday's critical thinking scale (SCTS) items?
3. What are the distracter indices of the Sunday's critical thinking scale (SCTS) items?

This study is of great importance to; the students, evaluators and psychometrician, university students and other stake holders. Firstly, evaluators or psychometricians will be encourage to always find out the authenticities of developed instrument, to ensure that they are in the proper standard ; especially, on item analysis indices, to be sure of items goodness in terms of difficulties, discriminative and distractive indices. Also, both university students and other levels of scholars, as well as candidate that will go for job tests or placement tests will have authentic test items to answer that will enhance their critical thinking levels without been presented with confused instruments.

Other stake holders, such as; Tertiary institutions, WAEC; NECO and different measurement and evaluation bodies or departments in business areas; will regularly invite experts in measurement and evaluation disciplines (psychometricians) to corroborate testing instruments with the use of item analysis indices, so that the candidates writing those exams will not be experiencing the challenges that occurs in erotic instruments.

Methodology

This study adopted an Ex-Post Facto design; based on the secondary instrument on critical thinking scale, an this type of design is adopted if the instrument has already been designed or developed, it is also called an after effect research design (Zainab and Devin, 2022). This study has a population of 34,665 of 300 level students that are attending the federal universities in south-south part of Nigeria; the reason is because this category of under graduate are expected to manifest thinking critical skills in their school works and if they find themselves outside the school to achieve their purposes of attaining tertiary education. Multistage sampling procedure of three (3) stages; purposive, proportionate stratified and purposive were used to draw the sample of 1, 0 41 participants from the population. The instrument titled; Sunday Dorathy's Critical Thinking Scale (SCTS) for University Students was adopted to collect data for this study, the items were dichotomously scored in right and wrong format of which only one of the options was correct, while others were distracters that may have led the respondents to think critically and to successfully elicit information as regards the extent to which they can handle critical thinking tasks. The specifications of the task of this study that were corroborated were the seven (7) domains of critical thinking, which includes; Inductive, Deductive, Analysis, Assumption, Definition, Interpretation and Problem solving. The test item format and the length were based on fifty (50) multiple choice objectives test type only and it consisted of three options of A, B and C under each stem of the instruction. Sunday's Critical Thinking Scale (DCTS) was validated in different areas such as; face, construct and content validities through experts in measurement and evaluation, psychology as well as English language, and the corrections were made adequately. Sunday's Critical Thinking Scale reliability was established after collecting data from the 300 level students for pilot study from similar universities through Kuder Richardson 21 and the reliability coefficient was 0.89 after administering it to the third year student in a similar institution; state

universities in the area of the study, the instrument was reversed for the final administration. The data collected for this study was analyze with; difficulty indices, discriminating indices and distractive indices.

RESULTS

Research Question 1: What are the difficulty indices of the Dorathy’s critical thinking scale (SCTS) items?

Table 1: Research question 8 scores of the critical thinking scale (SCTS) items were answered using difficulty indices; the results are presented in table 1.

ITEMS.	DI.	ITEMS.	DI.	ITEMS	DI.	ITEMS	DI.
1	0.62	14	0.50	27	0.41	40	0.45
2	0.49	15	0.69	28	0.38	41	0.37
3	0.64	16	0.71	29	0.40	42	0.38
4	0.27	17	0.67	30	0.50	43	0.32
5	0.31	18	0.60	31	0.36	44	0.35
6	0.49	19	0.66	32	0.41	45	0.33
7	0.48	20	0.40	33	0.42	46	0.36
8	0.30	21	0.32	34	0.35	47	0.32
9	0.28	22	0.44	35	0.61	48	0.37
10	0.50	23	0.51	36	0.61	49	0.31
11	0.36	24	0.27	37	0.53	50	0.35
12	0.48	25	0.27	38	0.55		
13	0.62	26	0.48	39	0.51		

Foot Note: The alphabets **DI** Inside the top of the table is a representative of the word Difficulty Indices.

Table 1 revealed that difficulty indices of Sunday’s critical thinking scale DCTS ranged from 0.71 to + 0.27, 4 items out of the 50 items were most difficult, hence they are adequate to be included in the 3rd year students critical thinking scale based on the bench mark because they are still within the range of 0.20 and they are few, the items are: 4, 24, 25 and 9. There were no item with 0.90 and above, so the instrument does not contain very easy items and no item was below 0.20 and, these items are: 1, 2, 3, 5, 6, 7, 8, , 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19, 20, 21, 22, 23, 26, 27, 27, 28, 29, 30, 31, 32, 33, 34, 35, 36, 37, 38, 39, 40, 41, 42, 43, 44, 45, 46, 47, 48, 49 and 50 which ranges from 0.24- 0.71.

Research Question 2: What are the discriminating indices of the Dorathay’s critical thinking scale (DCTS) items?

Table 2: To answer this research question 2, the scores of the items were obtained using Discriminating indices; the results are presented in table 2.

ITEMS	DI.	ITEMS	DI	ITEMS	DI
1	0.29	19	0.38	37	0.39
2	0.23	20	0.35	38	0.36
3	0.34	21	0.28	39	0.61
4	0.17	22	0.40	40	0.40
5	0.18	23	0.42	41	0.21
6	0.36	24	0.59	42	0.17
7	0.30	25	0.22	43	0.31
8	0.25	26	0.38	44	0.25
9	0.26	27	0.25	45	0.15
10	0.37	28	0.14	46	0.53
11	0.21	29	0.30	47	0.29
12	0.36	30	0.39	48	0.25
13	0.39	31	0.27	49	0.34
14	0.60	32	0.58	50	0.59
15	0.31	33	0.27		
16	0.26	34	0.30		
17	0.29	35	0.33		
18	0.41	36	0.37		

Foot Note: The alphabets DI Inside the top of the table is a representative of the word Discriminating Indices Table 2 revealed that the items discriminating indices of Sunday’s CTS ranged from 0.61 to 0.20, out of the 50 items were every good items they are; 39, 32, 46, , 14, 24 and 50, hence they can be adequate to be included in the 3rd year students critical thinking scale based on the bench mark while 26 items were reasonably good, they are; 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 28, 29, 30, 31, 32, 33, 34, 35, 36, 37, 38, 40, 41, 42, 43, 44, 45 and 47, 48. 19 items were on the border line, they are; 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19, 20, 21, 22, 23, 49s, 25, 26, 27. Hence, the researcher actually developed items that adequately discriminated effectively which enhanced the students to think critically.

Research Question 3: What are the distracter indices of the Sunday’s critical thinking scale (DCTS) items? **Table 3:** To answer this research question 10, the scores of the items were realized using Distractive indices; the results are presented in table 3.

ITEMS	OPTIONS	INDICES AND KEYS	REMARKS
1	A	0.32	Reasonably Distractive
	B	Key	Correct Answer
	C	0.41	Reasonably Distractive
2	A	Key	Correct Answer
	B	0.41	Reasonably Distractive
	C	0.33	Reasonably Distractive
3	A	Key	Correct Answer
	B	0.41	Reasonably Distractive

	C	0.41	Reasonably Distractive
4	A	0.38	Reasonably Distractive
	B	0.44	Reasonably Distractive
	C	Key	Correct Answer
5	A	0.28	Reasonably Distractive
	B	0.61	Very Distractive
	C	Key	Correct Answer
6	A	Key	Correct Answer
	B	0.30	Reasonably Distractive
	C	0.25	Reasonably Distractive
7	B	Key	Correct Answer
	B	0.30	Reasonably Distractive
	C	0.25	Reasonably Distractive
8	A	0.27	Reasonably Distractive
	B	0.27	Reasonably Distractive
	C	Key	Correct Answer
9	A	0.28	Reasonably Distractive
	B	0.25	Reasonably Distractive
	C	Key	Correct Answer
10	A	0.46	Reasonably Distractive
	B	0.45	Reasonably Distractive
	C	Key	Correct Answer
11	A	0.33	Reasonably Distractive
	B	0.40	Reasonably Distractive
	C	Key	Correct Answer
12	A	0.62	Very Distractive
	B	Key	Correct Answer
	C	0.51	Moderately Distractive
13	A	0.59	Moderately Distractive
	B	Key	Correct Answer
	C	0.63	Very Distractive

14	A B C	0.40 0.25 Key	Reasonably Distractive Reasonably Distractive Correct Answer
15	A B C	0.34 0.42 Key	Reasonably Distractive Reasonably Distractive Correct Answer
16	A B C	0.27 0.28 Key	Reasonably Distractive Reasonably Distractive Correct Answer
17	A B C	0.29 Key 0.35	Reasonably Distractive Correct Answer Reasonably Distractive
18	A B C	0.30 0.25 Key	Reasonably Distractive Reasonably Distractive Correct Answer
19	A B C	0.28 0.53 Key	Reasonably Distractive Reasonably Distractive Correct Answer
20	A B C	0.27 0.61 Key	Reasonably Distractive Very Distractive Correct Answer
21	A B C	0.34 0.29 Key	Reasonably Distractive Reasonably Distractive Correct Answer
22	A B C	0.32 0.49 Key	Reasonably Distractive Reasonably Distractive Correct Answer
23	A B C	0.50 Key 0.55	Moderately Distractive Correct Answer Moderately Distractive
24	A B C	Key 0.38 0.42	Correct Answer Reasonably Distractive Reasonably Distractive
25	A B C	0.29 0.33 Key	Reasonably Distractive Reasonably Distractive Correct Answer
26	A B C	0.32 Key 0.27	Reasonably Distractive Correct Answer Reasonably Distractive

27	A B C	Key 0.28 0.49	Correct Answer Reasonably Distractive Reasonably Distractive
28	A B C	0.39 0.50 Key	Reasonably Distractive Moderately Distractive Correct Answer
29	A B C	Key 0.43 0.38	Correct Answer Reasonably Distractive Reasonably Distractive
30	A B C	0.54 0.50 Key	Moderately Distractive Moderately Distractive Correct Answer
31	A B C	Key 0.38 0.29	Correct Answer Reasonably Distractive Reasonably Distractive
32	A B C	0.44 Key 0.23	Reasonably Distractive Correct Answer Distractive
33	A B C	Key 0.41 0.50	Correct Answer Reasonably Distractive Moderately Distractive
34	A B C	0.54 Key 0.20	Moderately Distractive Correct Answer Distractive
35	A B C	0.41 0.37 Key	Reasonably Distractive Reasonably Distractive Correct Answer
36	A B C	0.27 Key 0.32	Reasonably Distractive Correct Answer Reasonably Distractive
37	A B C	0.37 Key 0.47	Reasonably Distractive Correct Answer Reasonably Distractive
38	A B C	0.36 0.29 Key	Reasonably Distractive Reasonably Distractive Correct Answer
39	A B C	0.36 0.89 Key	Reasonably Distractive highly Distractive Correct Answer

40	A B C	0.44 Key 0.33	Reasonably Distractive Correct Answer Reasonably Distractive
41	A B C	0.41 0.54 Key	Reasonably Distractive Moderately Distractive Correct Answer
42	A B C	0.45 Key 0.48	Reasonably Distractive Correct Answer Reasonably Distractive
43	A B C	0.47 Key 0.50	Reasonably Distractive Correct Answer Moderately Distractive
44	A B C	0.40 0.51 Key	Reasonably Distractive Moderately Distractive Correct Answer
45	A B C	0.51 Key 0.41	Moderately Distractive Correct Answer Reasonably Distractive
46	A B C	0.21 0.78 Key	Distractive Highly Distractive Correct Answer
47	A B C	0.58 0.50 Key	Moderately Distractive Moderately Distractive Correct Answer
48	A B C	0.54 Key 0.59	Moderately Distractive Correct Answer Moderately Distractive
49	A B C	0.63 0.48 Key	Very Distractive Reasonably Distractive Correct Answer
50	A B C	0.67 0.49 Key	Moderately Distractive Reasonably Distractive Correct Answer

Table 3 revealed that, the distractive indices ranged from 0.89 to 0.32, 2 items out of 50 items were highly distractive indices they are; item 39 of option B and item 46 of option B while 6 items were very distractive and item 5, 12, 13, 20, 49 and 50 of option B, A,C, B, A, A. 25 distractive indices and above were moderately distractive, they are; item 49, 48, 47, 45, 44, 43, 34, 33, 30, 28, 23, 20, 19, 13, 12, 7, 5 of option A, A, A and C, A and B, A,B, C, A, C, A and B, A and C, B, B, C, A, C. 23 items were reasonably distractive, the items are; 50,49, 46, 45, 44, 43, 42, 41, 40 39, 38, 37, 36, 35,34, 33, 32, 31, 30, 29, 28, 27, 26, 25, 24, 22, 21, 19, 18, 17, 16, 15,

14, 11, 10, 9, 8, 7, 6, 5, 4, 3, 2, and 1 of options B, B, A, C, A, A, A and B, A, A, A, A and B, A and C, A and C, A and B, A and C, B and C, A and C, Band C, B and C, A, B and C, A and C, A and B, B and C, A and B, A and B, A, A and B, A and C, A and B, B and C, B and C, A, A and B, B and C, B and C, A and C respectively. The word keys in the table are the correct answers; only one the keys among the three options appears; A, B and C in each item and they were supposed to be chosen by the students who think critically, while the other two incorrect options are the distractors. The keys were not calculated because they do not need distractive indices estimations; they were not meant to distract the test takers.

Discussions

For item analysis, the item difficulty indices of Sunday's CTS Result of research question eight shows that the 50 DCTS items had difficulty indices that ranged acceptably. It means that the DCTS covers a very large converged of the three hundred levels of university students thinking critically. This is in agreement of the fact that difficulty levels of items were classified into various categories as indicated in Table 9 that items with 0.90 difficulty indices and above are easy, and 0.20- 0.90 are moderate items (Iweka 2014, Orulwene 2012 and Sabri, 2013). Hence, the difficulty standard as said by other researchers obtained in this study is within agreed range. This result realized may be due to varied critical thinkers that consist of the sample, speed of the critical thinkers (third year students), guessing, the length of the test, duration, extent of DCTS domains covered. This is because generalizability theory assumes that the sources of variation in one facet universe may be individual differences among test takers, variation in individual item difficulty levels. (Cronbach, Nwageswari and Gleser 1972). This means that for students to think critically it is dependent on the student's experiences gotten from their individual educational attainment, even random variations like noise making.

Critical pedagogy drawn from critical thinking is seen as an educational journey surrounded with emotion and lay down rules to enable university students realize freedom, notice some antecedence and relate what has been learnt to have authority and ability to accurately embark on constructive activities (action) in the educational system and society as a whole (Groux, 2010).

This is because various critical pedagogy that lecturers exposes the students to may include familiar domains to some students and very strange to other students. Also, some lecturers may consider presenting their lectures in a way that will instigate critical thinking while some may not, these can lead to different factors into the student's critical thinking in the universities. Again, the sample of the study is made up of students from the same three hundred levels', this does not mean that they have the same speed of the critical thinking in responding to task given to them. This proves that some students may be at same levels with their year mates but have lower speed of answering or solving critical thinking items, so in order to avoid submitting empty script the guess to ensure that they have responded to all the questions whether wrong or right, this may have affected the result of this study. To enhance the determination of difficulty indices; Morgado, Meireles, Neves, Amaral, and Ferrerira (2017) recommendation that future research practices based on different item development that will be adopted to create assessment of items with theories and psychometric approaches and current practices should be evaluated in terms of filling in the gaps, matching, essay etc of item generation. difficulty indices are purposeful in diver's ways in that it indicates the concept that require to be reemphasized when discover that students cannot answer most question right because they are hard and it is an identification of the strength and weakness of the construct or domain given feedback from the students on the aspect as well as revealing the item bias.

Also, the discriminating indices of the Sunday Dorathy's CTS items result indicates that the estimated discriminating indices that ranges that was adequate means a high discrimination index for most of the items.

These finding is in agreement with the assertion that discriminating levels of items were classified into five categories as items with 0.50 discriminating indices and above are very high or good, and 0.30- 0.39 are reasonably good items, boarder line are item from 0.20-0.29 while the poor items are from below 0.19 (Iweka, 2014; Opara, 2016; Orulwene, 2012). In this study no item discriminated in the negative direction, it means that majority of the respondents who have achieved more or who can adequately think critically were choosing the correct answers while those who did not or who could not really think critically as it showed in their responses also chose some of the items correctly.

One of the factors that may be responsible for this result may be the study sample, the internal relationship of the items as well as item generation methods. To support this, discrimination estimates depends on factors such like type of test, ambiguity worded and if the results are showing negative or positive. The most vital validity benchmark for items such as the critical think scale is that whether a student got an item correct or not is because of their level of thinking or reasoning and not due to another factor like chance or test bias (Christine, 2019). It continued that this type of measure is expected to have internal consistency consist of items with mostly positive relationships with total test score (<https://www.washington.edu/assessment/scanning-scoring/scoring/reports/item-analysis/>)

Furthermore, the distracter indices of the Sunday's CTS result unveil that the determined distractive indices items prove moderately distractive indices for majority of the items. This outcome is based on the fact that distractive indices of items were classified into various categories as indicated in the previous studies that items with 0.70 indices and above are highly distractive indices while 0.60 distractive indices are considered to be very distractive, 0.50 distractive indices and above are moderately distractive, and 0.20-0.49 are reasonably distractive items, (Orulwene, 2012). Also, Christine (2019) opined that items are said to be effectively distractive if they attract test takers with a lower overall score more than the test takers that with a higher overall score. In relating it to this study the critical thinking scale items really distracted students in the lower group as supposed. Item distractor may be functional or effective where about three options out of four options of a stem are not correct that may be choosing to be very low percentage of respondents or more of them and the efficiency of distractor may range from about 0.20 (Sing, 2017).

Summary of Findings

1. The difficulty indices of 50 SCTS items range from 0.71 to 0.27.
2. The discriminating indices of 50 SCTS items range from 0.61 to 0.15.
3. The distractive indices of 50 SCTS items range from 0.89 to 0.32.

Conclusions

The SCTS has very good ranges of item indices of its difficulty, discriminative and distractive indices.

Recommendations

Due to the dynamism in the globe; evaluators or psychometricians should always find out the authenticities of developed instrument; especially, on item analysis indices to be sure of its goodness in terms of difficulties, discriminative and distractive indices institution and organizational uses.

Other stake holders, such as; university institutions, WAEC; NECO and different measurement and evaluator bodies or departments in business organizations; should regularly invite experts in measurement and evaluation disciplines to corroborate the instrument they intend to be using; either for assessment, placement etc.

REFERENCE

- Abdulghani, H. M., Amad, F., Ponnamparuma, G. G., Khall, M. S., and Aldress, A. (2014). The relationship between non-functioning distracters and item difficulty of multiple choice questions. A descriptive analysis, 2(4).
- Bailin, M, B. (2009). Inquiry: A dialectal approach to teaching critical thinking. In JuhoRitotal (Ed.), Argument cultures: proceedings of OSSA 09, CO-ROM Windsor,ON: OSSA.
- Christine, L. (2019). What is item analysis and other important exam design principles. <https://www.turnitin.com/blog/what-is-item-analysis-and-other-important-exam-design-principles>
- Groux, H. A. (2010). Less From Paulo Freire. The chronicle higher education. <https://www.chic.edu/article/lesson-from-paulo-freire>
- Hamby, B. (2014). The Virtues Critical Thinkers, Doctoral dissertation, philosophy. Mc master university.
- Iweka, F. (2014). Comprehensive guide to test construction and administration. OmokuChifas Nigerian.
- Kpolovie, P. J. (2014). Test, measurement and evaluation in education. 2nd edition. Owerri: Springfield publishers Ltd.
- Mahjabeen W. Alam S and Hassan U (2018) Difficulty Index, Discriminating Index and Distracter Efficiency in Multiple Choice Questions. www. Researchgate.net
- Marcelo C. (2023) Why is critical Thinking Important? A survival Guide. uopeople.edu.
- Melyabeen, A., Hassan, Z., Butt, K., and Rizvic. (2018). Difficulty index, Discrimination index and Distractor Efficiency in multiple Choice.
- Morgado, F. R., Meireles, J. F. F., Neves, C. M., Amaral, A. C. S., and Ferrerira, C. E. M. (2017). Scale Development: ten main limitations and recommendations to improve future research practices. Springer open. www.sielo.br/pdf/prc/v30/1673-7153-prc-54115-5-016-0057-1.pdf
- MRCPCH, F., and Yus, M. S. B. (2014). Difficulty index, Discriminating index, sensitivity and specificity of long case and multiple choice questions to predict medical students examination performance. Journal of Taibah University Medical sciences, 9(2).
- Opara, I. M. (2016). Test Construction and Measurement Concepts and Application. Owerri: Career Publisher

Dr. Wali, Dorathy Wokunuchi and Dr. Ogunka Richard I (2025)

- Orluwene, G. W. and Sunday. D (2020) Learning Styles and Critical Thinking among Undergraduates of University of Port Harcourt. Archives of Current Research International, 20(1):56-64, 2020: article no.Acri.55834. ISSN: 2454-7077
- Orluwene, G. W. (2012). Introduction to Test Theory and Development Process. Port Harcourt: Chris- Ron Integrated Service.
- PPUKM. (2015). Calculating Difficulty, Discrimination and Reliability Index/standard Error of Measurement. <https://proidotorg.wordexpress.com>
- Sabri, S. (2013). Item analysis of students comprehensive test for research in teaching beginners string enabling using model based teaching among music students in public universities. International Journal of Education Research, 1(2).
- Sing, R. (2017). Item and distracter analysis of multiple choice questions (MCQ) prelinacy examination of undergraduate medical school. International Journal of Research in Medical Science, 5.
- Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophical. (2018). Critical Thinking. <https://plato.stanford.edu/edu/entrie>
- Stanovich, K., and EStanovich, P. J. (2010). A frame work for critical thinking, rational thinking, and intelligence. In D. p. David and R. J. Sternberg (Eds.), innovations educational psychology perspectives on Learning Teaching and Human Development. New York: Springer Publishing.
- Sunday. D and Orluwene, G. W (2021) Application of Generalizability Theory in the Estimation of Critical Thinking Scale for University Students. European Academic Research Vol. VII, Issue 7/July 2021, ISSN 2286-4822,
- Sunday. D and F.O.E Iweka (2021) Construct Validity of Critical thinking Scale for University Students in South-South Geo-Political Zone of Nigeria. Nigeria Journal of Emperical Studies in Psychology and Education (NJESPE). A Journal of Educational Psychology G&C, Faculty of Education, University of Port Harcourt, ISSN: 1595-4870. Volume 22, NO.1 January, 2020
- Tare M..E, Sameh R.I and Samiha (2018) Difficulty, Discrimination Indices of Sample of Typical Multiple Choice Questions Administered to Students at Different Levels. International Journal of Chem Tech Research, VoI 11, No. 50, PP 348-352
- ZainabS. Devin K. (2022) What is an Ex Post Facto Design. Sudy.com